

Biodiversity and conservation in the KwaMandlangampisi Protected Environment (KPE): Annual Report for 2025

Jeff W Morris

A report to the Management of the KPE

The KPE is situated in Mpumalanga, about 20km from the village of Lüneburg, which is across the border in KwaZulu-Natal. The KPE covers approximately 30,000ha. The first phase of the protected environment declaration was gazetted in 2010 and has remained in effect since. The land is privately owned, except for the Paardeplaas Nature Reserve, which is owned by the Mpumalanga Tourism and Parks Authority (MTPA). Details are available in the current Management Plan (MTPA 2025). Commercial farming activities are the order of the day with free-range livestock (cattle and sheep), some commercial forestry, and irrigated cash-crop cultivation in the area.

During the first three months of the year, the list of mammals compiled in 2010, when the protected environment was proclaimed, was [updated](#). This was a citizen science project by Jeff Morris. As many residents as possible were contacted, and individual animal lists from the three-month observation window were obtained. This was compiled into a new list that included a couple of species not in the original. The most interesting observations:

- Bushpig was not recorded in 2010 but is now a pest. Other new observations include Bat-eared Fox, Brown Hyaena, Large Spotted Genet, Scrub Hare, Rock Hyrax, Yellow- and other species of Mongoose, Polecat, Porcupine, Southern Reedbuck, and Steenbok.
- The number of species has almost doubled from 22 to 39. A difference in sampling methodology could have contributed. Naturalised and introduced animals are also now included.
- There are two Endangered, three Vulnerable, and five Near-threatened species.

It is prudent to establish water quality benchmarks in the event of a future major pollution spill. To this end, water samples were collected in July from both the Ntombe and Sibandlu Rivers for analysis. As we expected, water quality is excellent. The samples were collected during a low-flow period. Sampling was repeated in January 2026, when the rivers were at their peak. The report on this work was recently [published](#), with the following main findings. Principal component analysis (PCA) identified three primary drivers of water quality: mineralisation (PC1), seasonal shifts in alkalinity (PC2), and anthropogenic impact (PC3). While both rivers are remarkably clean by national standards, the Ntombe River exhibits a consistently higher and more persistent "pollution fingerprint" (elevated *E. coli* and Nitrates) compared to the Sibandlu River. This difference is attributed to irrigated cultivation and homesteads in the Ntombe catchment, whereas the Sibandlu remains undeveloped. The study confirms that while rainfall volume significantly dilutes mineral concentrations, the Ntombe River's pollution sources remain stable regardless of flow level, whereas the Sibandlu River's microbial profile is more flow-dependent and dynamic. Water analysis costs were sponsored by a landowner.

Then, with a grant of R40 000 from the Comondale Farmers' Association, a limnologist was contracted to undertake [a basic survey](#) of the invertebrates and fish in our rivers. He noted that the aquatic ecosystems were largely in their natural state. He found one possible new species of Mayfly. One Near Threatened fish species was found, and we are grateful that no exotic fish species were noted. One of the owners provided free self-catering accommodation for the researcher.

Professor Kevin Balkwill from Wits University spent a very productive four-day weekend based on Grootshoek. He brought his Mpumalanga Plant Specialist Group (PSG), comprising more than 20 enthusiasts. They also had free self-catering arrangements in one of the homes. The list of plants on iNaturalist grew significantly after their visit. One of the specialists has offered to compile a comprehensive checklist of plant taxa for us, including iNaturalist records and herbarium specimens. The botanist and two fellow botanists will visit again in February and will then write us a comprehensive report.

One participant with the PSG, an ornithologist, compiled a comprehensive list of more than 120 birds observed or heard during the period. This has been expanded into a [checklist of the birds](#) of the KPE, including a comparison with the Wakkerstroom bird 'hot spot'. The key findings of the report are as follows.

Biodiversity: The KPE supports 17 bird species of conservation concern.

Unique Species: Data analysis reveals 30 species present in the KPE that are not found in Wakkerstroom, likely due to the KPE's greater habitat diversity.

Survey Gaps: The area is currently under-recorded compared to its neighbour; while Wakkerstroom has 1,384 Full Protocol (Fp) cards and 322 species, the KPE has only 229 Fp cards and 236 species.

Rare Sightings: 56 species have been recorded only once or twice, including "specials" such as Botha's Lark, African Spoonbill, and Jacobin's Cuckoo.

A critical concern highlighted is the funding risk facing the SABAP2 database, which is the primary source for this birding data and a cornerstone of collaborative avian conservation in Africa.

This was followed by the first phase of a professional biodiversity assessment of eight farms within the protected environment in late spring. Each owner will pay their share of the total cost, which is close to R200 000. We will not be getting the results until after the second phase of fieldwork in February. Based on their brief interim report, the consultants (The Biodiversity Company) appear to have covered the area comprehensively. Owners are providing free accommodation for the researchers.

The last project for the year is underway. With a R30 000 grant from Edumbe Agri Centre NPC, Paulpietersburg, six students from the local community were tasked with [collecting ecological data and taking iNaturalist observations](#). They walked, rode horseback, and drove to cover as much of the rugged terrain as possible. Further data editing is needed before a final report can be produced. A mobile app was developed to collect data and capture field photographs. A database has been created to store all results for future reference. The author aims to establish a baseline of photographs taken at fixed points. In 20 or more years, someone will be able to visit the exact same sites and discern what has changed. Statistics of data loaded into the KPE SQLite database are as follows (end January 2026):

Total records – 606

Total photographs – 1540

Total videos – 5

Here is a map showing the locations where samples have been collected. The majority are on Groothoek and Donkerhoek. Data from other remote areas has still to be accessioned.

An estimated 100 additional samples and approximately 500 additional photos must still be downloaded from phones and accessioned.

The plan is to create a data vault on [Zenodo](https://zenodo.org/) for the long-term retention of this data, particularly the photographs. For those who are unfamiliar with it, Zenodo is a free, open-access, catch-all digital repository for research outputs. It enables researchers in any field to share, preserve, and cite data, software, and publications, with each submission assigned a persistent DOI. Zenodo is designed for long-term preservation, with a commitment to retain your data for the lifetime of the repository. This is currently defined as at least the next 20 years, aligned with the operational lifespan of the host laboratory, CERN. Should the repository close, Zenodo commits to making best efforts to migrate your content to another suitable, long-term archive.

Cumulative plot of the number of observations per month since 2021. Inset, most active observers.

The year has contributed nearly 2,000 observations to the [KPE iNaturalist project](#). An extract of all biota and all states since observations in the KPE’s area began yielded 4579 observations. The peak month was November 2025, with 1948 observations, and the total for the year was 3,271. In November, 2025, the main contributors were the PSG team, Intando Yemvelo team, and The Biodiversity Company.

Going forward. What are our plans? We are seeking a herpetologist to conduct a baseline survey for us, assuming we can secure sponsorship. Another idea is to collect all historical rainfall records from local farmers for long-term curation. In the context of climate change, such records, if sufficiently numerous, could be valuable.

2026-02-21

